

Parc Natural
de l'Alt Pirineu

UAB

CREAF

BAT HABITAT USE IN THE PYRENEES

THE CASE OF THE PARC NATURAL DE L'ALT PIRINEU

MÁSTER EN ECOLOGÍA TERRESTRE Y GESTIÓN DE LA BIODIVERSIDAD

TRABAJO DE FIN DE MÁSTER

ESPECIALIDAD EN ECOLOGÍA TERRESTRE

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PARTICIPATION

The elaboration of this study started in 2020, when the Parc Natural de L'Alt Pirineu decided to track their bat populations, which began with the installation of ultrasound recorders during the summers of 2021 and 2022. In October 2022, I joined the project and became involved in the sound identification of these recordings. This phase was particularly time-intensive (~ 70 hours), due to the initial learning curve and the substantial amount of material to be processed (around 600 hours of recordings). This stage was conjointly conducted with Elisenda Montserrat. After processing the recordings, and under the guidance of both Oriol and Elisenda, I autonomously finished the present work. During this phase, I selected the relevant information for the study, organised it, conducted statistical analysis, browsed literature, and wrote the present manuscript. Additionally, from June 10th to October 12th 2023, thanks to the 'Campus Rural' grant, I had the opportunity to work face-to-face with the management team of the Parc, learning and contributing to the bat recording efforts, and participating in the development of the new bat monitoring programme.

CRediT ROLES

Luis Górriz Huarte: conceptualization, formal analysis, visualisation, writing (original draft, review and editing). Elisenda Montserrat Freixa: conceptualization, supervision, writing (review and editing). Oriol Grau Fernández: conceptualization, supervision, writing (review and editing). Adrià López Baucells: conceptualization.

SCI MAGAZINE

For this study we chose to follow the guidelines of '**Journal of Mammalogy**', a highly recognised research journal included within the SCI in 2023, with an impact factor of 2.291. Journal of Mammalogy comprises a well-defined section on bat research, and has clear and easy-following author guidelines, which we applied to the present work (Oxford Academic 2023).

ETHICS AND CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS

The authors confirm that no conflict of interest occurred during the preparation of this work, that all employed techniques, such as acoustic monitoring, were non-invasive for bats, and that all sensible natural areas were accessed with the consequent permits. The authors also affirm that the present work is original, and not published or in process of publishing elsewhere.

Declaration of directors

Both directors, Elisenda Montserrat Freixa, and Oriol Grau Fernández, and academic tutor Bernat Claramunt López, declare that the present work has been performed and finished successfully, during summer 2023.

In Llavorsí, Lleida. 7th August 2023:

Elisenda Montserrat Freixa

Oriol Grau Fernández

Bernat Claramunt López

ABSTRACT

1 Bats represent one of the most diverse and endangered animal groups on earth, playing essential
2 roles in ecosystems and offering multiple benefits to society. To support their conservation, it
3 is crucial to understand their habitat requirements, which has become more feasible thanks to
4 the recent development of affordable ultrasound recorders. This changing paradigm allowed us,
5 for the first time, to place bat ultrasound recorders around 59 sampling points within the Parc
6 Natural de L'Alt Pirineu (NE of the Iberian Peninsula), one of the largest and most relevant
7 protected areas within the Pyrenees. After species identification, we modelled the influence of
8 relevant predictor variables on bat activity, we checked the richness patterns in our area,
9 analysed the habitat selection of each bat species, and we plotted species and habitats
10 assemblages. Our findings suggest that the negative impact of altitude on bat activity is
11 primarily subrogated to the habitat type, being strongly buffered within forests and aquatic
12 habitats. Bat richness peaked within bottom valley meadows, probably due to their transitional
13 position between woodlands and water habitats. We also found interesting differences within
14 species assemblages in both lakes and rivers, suggesting that bat morphology can greatly
15 determine aquatic habitat preference by bats. Finally, we report interesting observations of both
16 *Rinolophus euryale* and *R. ferrumequinum* at high altitudes, which could be due to sex
17 segregation, large distance flying or particularly high roosting sites.

Key words: altitude, *Barbastella*, forest maturity, mountain lakes, *Rhinolophus*, richness.

INTRODUCTION

18 Bats encompass one of the most diverse and astonishing animal groups on earth, comprising
19 around 1449 mammal species which inhabit all over the world, except for extreme polar
20 latitudes (COL 2023). They are known to maintain key ecosystem roles such as insect
21 regulation, pollination, and seed dispersal (Kunz et al. 2011), and have been repeatedly
22 proposed as effective ecosystem indicators to track habitat health (Jones et al. 2009). However,
23 their situation is critical. Scientists estimate that 23 % of bats are threatened globally and trends
24 of 53 % are still unknown (IUCN 2020), which evidences the urgent need to study and protect
25 this key and fascinating animal group.

26 As for any other species, protecting bats relies on a good understanding of their habitat
27 requirements. In this regard, bats are known to usually select water bodies for hunting, due to
28 the abundance of flies, mosquitos, moths, and other potential preys (Vaughan, Jones and Harris
29 1997.). But this initial premise has been found to be influenced by a great variety of factors.
30 Habitat structure, for instance, seems to be essential for bat communities, as a well-connected
31 landscape enables bats to better finding food and refugees (Walsh and Harris 1996). Micro-
32 topographical features can also pose relevant effects on bats; high tree density, for instance, can
33 difficult bats flying, and therefore reduce their presence in those sites, whereas edge habitats
34 can be used for orienting and easily feeding (Loeb and O'keefe 2006). Abiotic factors such as
35 climatological patterns or weather conditions (wind, temperature, rainfall, humidity, or even
36 moonlight), are also determinant in the presence and activity of bats, sometimes even between
37 two consecutive nights (Perks and Goodenough 2020). This is the reason why altitude and water
38 proximity have been suggested to greatly shape bat communities (Jaberg and Guisan, 2001;
39 Weier et al. 2017). Finally, and for more complexity, each bat species (within the Iberian
40 Peninsula, there are 32 recognised species (SECEMU 2018)) is differentially affected by all the
41 factors above, choosing habitat distinctly (Grindal and Brigham 1999).

42 All these findings reveal the enormous and intricate challenge of studying bat habitat use, which
43 turns even more demanding due to the particular characteristics of this mammals; nocturnal
44 discrete animals which emit no audible noise for humans and are able to fly for several
45 kilometres every night to eat. To overcome this defiance, scientists developed ultrasound
46 recorders, essential devices which can capture bat high-pitched noises and convert them into
47 the human audible spectrum, allowing for species identification. Unfortunately, these recorders
48 have traditionally been expensive and only available for specialised researchers, which has
49 greatly limited scientific advancements in many areas of the world (Ahlén and Baagøe 1999).
50 But fortunately, this paradigm has just changed. Only within the last few years, cheap
51 autonomous ultrasound detectors have been developed, allowing for citizens and unspecialized
52 nature managers to collect their own data from the field (Lim et al. 2021). This is the case of
53 “Parc Natural de l’Alt Pirineu” (PNAP), the largest protected area in Catalonia and within the
54 Spanish Pyrenees, whose workers, inspired by the citizen science project “Ratpenats” (MCNG
55 2019), started to track their own bat populations by disposing autonomous ultrasound recorders.
56 Thanks to the data collected from years 2021 and 2022 within the PNAP, we performed the
57 first global study about bat habitat use within the area, which sums up to the growing concern
58 of protected areas in Catalonia to protect this long-forgotten mammalian group.

59 With this regard, we hypothesised that: (h1) as stated by several researchers (Weier et al. 2017;
60 Coelho et al. 2018), altitude would have a strong negative effect over bat activity and would
61 determine the composition of bat community. (h2) Richness would slightly increase at first with
62 altitude, but then gradually drop until the mountain tops, matching the results of Piksa et al.
63 (2022) and other researchers. (h3) Forests would account for the lowest bat activity, and aquatic
64 habitats for the highest, reflecting the respective commuting and feeding activity of the bat
65 community (Jaberg and Guisan 2001). (h4) Habitat use of recorded species would fit within the
66 updated literature, such as in Dietz and Kiefer (2016).

METHODS

Study area

67 The PNAP comprises a large protected area within the Pyrenees, located within the Spanish
68 region of Catalonia, in between Andorra, France and the nearby region of Aragon. It ranges
69 from around ~ 700 meters above sea level (masl) until the highest peak in the whole region, the
70 Pica d'Estats (3143 masl). It currently comprises a total area of 79 317 ha, becoming in 2003
71 the largest protected area in Catalonia and within the Spanish Pyrenees (Generalitat de
72 Catalunya, 2003) (Fig. 1). Due to its large altitudinal gradient, biogeographical features,
73 extension, and low population density, PNAP remains as a highly diverse territory, being home
74 of a wide variety of ecosystems and species. It harbours 36 Habitats of Community Interest
75 (mountain lakes, wetlands, diverse grasslands, and well conserved old growth forests), as well
76 as a great list of protected species; the biggest Pyrenean populations of brown bear (*Ursus arctos*
77 L.) and capercaillie (*Tetrao urogallus* L.), key scavenger birds such as *Gypaetus barbatus* L. or
78 Egyptian vulture (*Neophron percnopterus* L.), rare plants like *Epipogium aphyllum*, and
79 protected lepidopters such as *Eriogaster catax* L. (Palau 2014). But most of all, and attaining
80 to this study, within all this rich ecosystem finds its home a healthy, diverse, but still mysterious
81 bat community.

Biodiversity monitoring plan

82 In order to protect and monitor its highly valuable habitats and species, PNAP created in 2007
83 its first biodiversity monitoring plan, or 'Pla de Seguiment de la Biodiversitat' (Montserrat-
84 Freixa et al. 2021). From then on, five different projects were performed to reveal the yet
85 unknown bat community, identifying a total number of 21 bat species, all of them protected and
86 16 considered endangered (Palomo et al. 2007). After this, PNAP decided to monitor and

87 evaluate the health of its bat community following the framework of ‘Ratpenats’, a precursor
88 citizen science project driven by the ‘Museu de Ciències Naturals de Granollers’ (MCNG),
89 which aims to track bat populations over Catalonia by revising caves, censusing bats in rivers,
90 and disposing ultrasound recorders over the territory (MCNG 2019).

Acoustic sampling

91 We deployed passive acoustic recorders (Audiomoth 1.2.0.) across multiple locations within
92 the PNAP during summers 2021 and 2022 (27 in 2021, and 32 in 2022). We sampled a total of
93 59 independent nights between July 1st and August 15th, as bat activity only peaks within this
94 period in this exigent mountainous region. In addition, to mitigate potential biases produced by
95 the emergence of bat’s offspring, we avoided collecting samples after August 15th. Recorders
96 were placed from 1.5 to 2 m high, always eluding rainy or windy nights which could potentially
97 influence bat activity. Recording commenced half an hour before sunset and concluded half an
98 hour after sunrise (Supplementary Data SD1).

99 We sampled 12 representative habitats within the Parc, aiming to cover the maximum
100 ecosystem diversity in our study area. These habitats included three aquatic environments
101 (rivers, reservoirs and mountain lakes), four forest types (*Pinus sylvestris* L., *Pinus uncinata*
102 Mill., *Abies alba* Mill, and *Quercus petraea* (Matt.) Liebl.) and five open habitats (montane
103 hayfields, alpine grasslands and bottom valley meadows, as well as rhododendron and broom
104 shrublands) (SD2). Rivers typically feature fast-flowing waters, bordered by a low forest
105 composed of *Alnus glutinosa* L. and *Fraxinus angustifolia* Vahl. And *Salix* spp. trees. Many of
106 these rivers have been strongly modified to create large bottom valley reservoirs, which often
107 support high biodiversity. On mountain tops, alpine lakes also sustain a range of interesting
108 species. Woodland types encompass *P. sylvestris* forests, often found within the shaded

109 submontane areas of the Parc. Below them, we find *Q. petraea* and *Q. pubescens* forests,
110 thriving in the lowest most humid areas, and occasionally mixed with other deciduous trees,
111 such as *Betula pendula* Roth. Finally, We also see *A. alba* stands, occupying the most humid
112 locations of the montane environment and giving way to the topmost woodlands of *P. uncinata*,
113 often linked to an understory of *Rhododendron ferrugineum* L. Open habitats include high south
114 facing rhododendron shrublands, north facing broom shrublands (*Genista balansae* (Boiss.)
115 Rouy), bottom valley meadows which are frequently cultivated for mowing, montane hayfields,
116 and alpine grasslands composed by *Nardus* spp., *Festuca* spp., and other herbaceous species
117 (Carreras et al. 2015).

Sound identification

118 Each night of recording generated around 120 sound archives of 5-minute duration (15 to 20
119 GB), which were sent to the 'Barcelona Supercomputer Center' using the Quirohabitats
120 platform. Here, a supercomputer split them into 5 second audio files, selecting only those with
121 potential 'bat passes', and pre-identifying them based on a series of algorithms. Next, we
122 manually identified all bat passes obtained from this process using the free software programme
123 Kaleidoscope (V.5.3.9). We converted the total number of bat passes per night for each species
124 to bat passes per hour, which enabled us to compare bat activity between different nights. The
125 concept of "bat pass" allows for a better standardisation of bat activity between studies,
126 consisting in the presence of at least two bat vocalisations within a recorded audio file of 5
127 seconds (SD3). Unfortunately, as it was stated by Russ (2012) some species calls are often
128 indistinguishable from each other, especially when they account for similar morphology and
129 habitat niche. This is the reason why we identified 6 species and 7 phonic groups, in which we
130 could not recognise between two or more probable species. The probable species on the area of

131 these groups were subtracted from previous inventories made by Flaquer et al. (2007, 2008,
132 2009, 2010), and can be consulted in Table 1.

Statistical analysis

Habitat analysis

133 After organising all our data (SD12), we commenced analysing it from two perspectives:
134 regarding habitats and regarding species. For habitats, we plotted bat activity and richness
135 depending on altitude in order to preliminarily detect the probable effect of this pattern (Fig. 2
136 and 3). We then tested simple average differences between habitats using t or wilcoxon tests
137 depending on group normality. Additionally, we bar-plotted all habitats, filling them as a
138 function of bat activity, to visually understand which species were more active in each
139 environment (SD4). We performed this same approach reversely with bat species, filling the
140 bars of each species with the corresponding proportion of calls per habitat (Supp Fig).

141 To achieve a more profound analysis and interpretation of our data, we tried to represent habitat
142 type depending on the bat community. To doing so, we plotted a Principal Component Analysis
143 (PCA) with package ‘PCAtools’ (Bligue 2020), where our 59 samples (dots) depended on the
144 13 bat species as explanatory vectors. Then, similarly to Del Arco et al. (2012), we coloured
145 samples depending on each habitat type, visualising the distribution of habitats within the
146 multivariate space (SD5). From this initial PCA, we grouped points according to habitat type
147 and then calculated the centroid for each. This allowed us to use ‘vegdist’ function from
148 package ‘vegan’ (Oksanen 2008), to calculate the distances between centroids. This distance
149 matrix was then used with package ‘Rtsne’ (Krijthe and Van Der Maaten 2022) to create a two-
150 dimensional representation of the distance between centroids, allowing us to interpret the
151 resemblance between habitats, based on their respective community composition.

Environmental predictors

152 After analysing our raw data, we developed mixed models to better understand how bat activity
153 and richness was influenced by a series of environmental variables. For all our sampling points,
154 we extracted a total of 11 quantitative environmental variables that, according to literature,
155 could influence bat activity and richness (SD12). After testing correlation between them, we
156 only kept 5 (altitude, hill shade, slope, night temperature and distance to water). The first three
157 variables were obtained from conversions in QGIS (V.3.32) of a digital model of elevations
158 (DEM) of the area. Each night temperature for every sample was extracted by accessing the
159 data from the nearest meteorological station to each point, belonging to the ‘Servei
160 Meteorològic de Catalunya’. Finally, distance to water was calculated by manually measuring
161 the interval between each point and the nearest rivers, reservoir or mountain lake in QGIS. We
162 kept altitude as a representative variable of both mean annual temperature and precipitation,
163 due to the high intercorrelation between them (positively correlated with precipitation and
164 negatively with temperature). Once potential predictors were selected, we created mixed linear
165 models and included the sampling spot as a random factor, by using the ‘lme4’ package (Bates
166 et al. 2014). We made 15 different models with total activity, richness, and the individual
167 activity of the 13 bat species. We then tested these models IN six different situations (all
168 samples, all samples without bottom water habitats, forests and open habitats, only forests, only
169 open habitats, and only aquatic habitats) aiming to elucidate from different points of view, the
170 effect of our fixed factors.

171 Once models were created, we used package ‘MuMin’ (Barton 2023), to calculate for each all-
172 possible combinations of fixed factors. We then used delta BIC as an indicator variable to
173 measure their resemblance selecting those that distanced < 2 delta BIC from the best model.
174 When several were considered as “best” we averaged them to get our best final model, as
175 explained by Burnham and Anderson (2004). We ended up calculating the relative explanatory

176 power (R²) of both fixed and random factors in our model, by using the method described by
177 Nakagawa and Schielzeth (2014), allowing us to know if our tested variables were or not
178 predictive. We performed this same process with all our models, and in all situations (total
179 activity, richness, and the activity of our 13 bat species).

RESULTS

Habitat analysis

180 From our 59 summer samples, we obtained 620 hours of recording with a total number
181 of 85 053 bat passes. From them 40 % corresponded to *Pippistrellus pippistrellus* Schr., 23 %
182 to *Myotis* 50, and 14 % to *Pipkuhnat*. The remaining corresponded to *Hypsugo savii* Bon. (7%),
183 *PippygMin* (6%), and *TadNyc* (6%) and a scarce ~2% to all *EptNycVes*, *Plecotus* spp.,
184 *Barbastella barbastellus* Schr., *Myotis* 30, *Rhinolophus euryale* Blas., *Rhinolophus*
185 *ferrumequinum* Schr. and *Rhinolophus hipposideros* Bech. (SD6).

186 Simple plotting and testing between habitats showed total activity to be significantly higher
187 within aquatic environments. Regarding bat richness, both aquatic and open environments
188 showed similar values, whereas the number of species within forests was significantly lower
189 (Fig. 2 and 3). When clustering habitat types and testing differences inside, we found slightly
190 higher activity within *A. alba* and *P. uncinata* compared to the rest of forests. For open habitats,
191 alpine grasslands showed significantly lower activity and richness than the rest, whereas bottom
192 valley meadows showed relevantly higher activity and richness (Fig. 5). Habitat distance map
193 showed four well defined groups: aquatic environments all together; *A. alba* and *P. uncinata*
194 forests; bottom valley meadows and rhododendron shrublands; and a big group composed by
195 *Q. petraea.*, *P. sylvestris* forests, altimontane hayfields, broom shrublands and alpine grasslands
196 (Fig. 4).

197 Regarding bat species (Supp Fig 8, 9, 10 & 11), *P. pippistrellus* activity peaked in aquatic
198 habitats, where we recorded more than 85 % of its calls, specially selecting bottom valley
199 reservoirs. Both Pipkuhnat, and Pippygmin (See Table 1) had a greater selection of open
200 habitats, maintaining like *P. pippistrellus* a reduced activity within forests. In this regard,
201 Pipkuhnat preferably selected rhododendron shrublands, whereas Pipygmin selected bottom
202 valley meadows. Myotis 50 (most probably *Myotis daubentonii* Kuhl) mostly selected bottom
203 valley reservoirs and rivers, and was poorly represented within mountain lakes. Myotis 30
204 (probably *Myotis myotis* Bork.), was more active on bottom reservoirs (~ 60% of calls) but was
205 also recorded within altimontane hayfields (~ 30 % of calls). The few calls detected in forests
206 for this last species were all at *P. uncinata* forests. As most species, *Plecotus* spp. were also
207 highly active in aquatic habitats, but interestingly, no call was recorded within rivers; only
208 within water reservoirs and mountain lakes. *Plecotus* spp. were also well representated in open,
209 selecting bottom valley meadows and altimontane hayfields. Barbastelle bat showed an equal
210 distribution of their calls within all habitats, respectively preferring *P. uncinata* woodlands,
211 bottom valley meadows, as well as aquatic reservoirs and rivers within aquatic habitats, with
212 no presence within mountain lakes. *H. savii* was mainly found in aquatic habitats, selecting as
213 other species both bottom reservoirs and mountain lakes, but almost never rivers. EptNycVes
214 (probably *Eptesicus serotinus* Schr. or *Nyctalus leisleri* Kuhl.) mostly selected aquatic habitats
215 of all types (see SD8). This phonic group also had a good number of calls within open habitats,
216 mainly selecting bottom valley meadows. TadNyc (probably *Tadarida teniotis* Raf.) was
217 mainly present in aquatic habitats, and, as other species, selected both reservoirs and mountain
218 lakes but never rivers. All *Rhinolophus* species were characterised for their complete absence
219 within forests and being mostly recorded within open habitats. *R. euryale* and *R. ferrumequinum*
220 were principally found in open habitats, concretely in broom shrublands and bottom valley
221 meadows respectively. In the case of *R. hipposideros*, it was present more or less equally in

222 both aquatic and open habitats, selecting altimontane pastures and rhododendron shrublands.
223 All *Rhinolophus*, when in aquatic habitats, were almost always in rivers and never in mountain
224 lakes.

Environmental predictors

225 After creating models for total bat activity, richness and the activity of the 13 species, we
226 observed a general negative effect of both altitude, slope and distance to water in most of the
227 models (Fig. 6). The best possible model for total bat activity included both altitude and slope
228 as the best explanatory variables, with a reverse correlation. For richness, only altitude was kept
229 as a good explanatory variable. When subsetting all samples without bottom aquatic habitats
230 (rivers and reservoirs), altitude was kept as the strongest negative predictor variable for
231 richness, but not for total bat activity. In the case of open habitats, altitude was again the best
232 predictor, for both richness and total activity. Within aquatic habitats, slope was the best
233 predictor of total activity, and night temperature was the strongest for richness. Finally, forest
234 models showed hillshade as the most relevant variable for total activity, and distance to water
235 for richness (SD11).

236 Regarding species, altitude and slope were generally the most common predictors. Some
237 species with a low number of recordings, such as *Rhinolophus* spp. presented different model
238 outputs, but we decided not to comment them, due to the lack of data within the model. The
239 best predictors for all cases, can be otherwise consulted in SD11. Finally, R2 values for total
240 activity accounted for an estimated 30% for fixed factors and 60 % for the random factor (site).

DISCUSSION

241 Altitude, slope, and distance to water appeared as the most relevant predictors in our models,
242 both inversely correlated with bat activity (Fig. 6; Table 2 and 3). This agrees with our initial
243 hypothesis for altitude (h1), which we expected to have a negative determinant effect over bat
244 activity and richness. The present results also match with existing literature, as both height and
245 water availability have been pointed out as the best predictors for explaining bat feeding
246 distribution (Weier et al. 2017; Coelho et al. 2018). However, when looking more carefully,
247 our results suggest that, despite being a relevant predictor, altitudinal effects remain strongly
248 subrogated to the habitat type and their outcomes could be buffered within both aquatic and
249 forest habitats.

250 In the case of aquatic habitats, mountain lakes supported similar bat activity than bottom valley
251 rivers and reservoirs (Fig. 2), so when deleting bottom reservoirs and rivers from model
252 analysis, altitude lost relevance or even turned out to have a positive effect on the activity of
253 some species (SD11). This is the case *Plecotus* spp., *TadNyc*, *H.savii* and *P. Pipistrellus*, which
254 seemed to concentrate for feeding both in bottom and top aquatic habitats, omitting an
255 altitudinal difference of ~ 2000 m and a mean temperature drop of about 5°C (SD8). This
256 partially matches with the findings at Jura Mountain (Switzerland) by researchers Jaberg and
257 Guisan (2001), who found aquatic habitats to be the strongest positive predictor within their
258 models. All of it suggests that despite posing challenging environmental conditions such as cold
259 temperatures and stronger winds, the great abundance of food within these mountain lakes could
260 make it profitable for bats to fly up and feed within these inhospitable locations. It is relevant
261 to remark, however, that sexual disparities could be occurring between bottom and top aquatic
262 habitats due to sexual segregation (Holzaidner and Zahn 2000). This phenomenon causes males
263 from some species like *Nyctalus lasiopterus* Schr. and *Plecotus auritus* L. to live in higher
264 altitudes during the roosting period, avoiding competition with females (McGuire and Boyle

265 2013). Unfortunately, these details could not be checked in our study, due to the lack of time
266 and resources to perform bat trapping and identification.

267 As in the case of aquatic habitats, forests seemed to buffer the negative altitudinal effect over
268 bat activity and richness, which completely matches the findings of the recent research by
269 Novella-Fernández et al. (2022). This is the case of *A. alba* and *P. uncinata* woodlands, which
270 despite being higher in altitude, supported greater bat activity than lower *P. sylvestris* and *Q.*
271 *petraea* forests, as well as accounting for a more similar bat community (Fig.4). The
272 explanation to this could rely on forest maturity, as higher *A. alba* and *P. uncinata* forests would
273 be less human managed, supporting older trees, and therefore a richer and more heterogeneous
274 habitat for bats (Ville Vasco et al. 2020). This hypothesis is supported by the presence of *B.*
275 *barbastellus* and *Myotis* spp. calls mainly within these woodland types (SD9), as they are both
276 pointed to depend on mature stands which are “richly structured and highly productive” (Russo
277 et al. 2004; Napal et al. 2013).

278 This determinant effect of habitat type over bat activity and richness is also visible within the
279 bat community assemblage (Fig.2), which seems greatly clustered by habitat structure rather
280 than shaped by other parameters such as altitude, matching the study of Kusch and Schotte
281 (2007) (See “Limitations”), and supporting the mentioned above. However, not all habitats
282 appear to buffer weather conditions. In the case of open landscapes, bat activity and richness
283 clearly dropped gradually as we increased in altitude. The lack of vegetation and their
284 exposition, could be the reason why these environments are highly affected by abiotic
285 parameters, reducing arthropod productivity, and therefore bat activity.

286 Apart from the discussion about altitudinal effects over bat activity, we found richness to be
287 distributed in an interesting way, differently to what we expected (h2). We anticipated an initial
288 increment with altitude and then a dropdown (humped curve), as lower and higher habitats

289 sometimes converge in a maximum diversity of bats (Williams et al. 2010; Piksa et al. 2022).
290 However, we found this only partially true. First, as we stated before, richness did not show an
291 altitudinal but an habitat pattern (Fig.3), especially within aquatic and forest habitat.
292 Interestingly, instead of a humped curve for richness, we found bottom valley meadows to
293 support the highest number of species of all habitats, which is surprising as they supported only
294 one sixth of the activity compared to aquatic habitats. The reason of this could be due to the
295 interface characteristics of bottom valley meadows, located in between surface water bodies
296 and forests, and therefore receiving species from all habitats, which is similar to the results
297 found by Kusch and Schotte (2007), and is partially supported by the review of McCain (2007).
298 This commuting movement of bats, from roosting and sleeping forest areas, into aquatic feeding
299 environments, matches with our third hypothesis (h3) and the existing literature for other
300 mountainous areas (Jaberg and Guisan 2001). Here, we expected and found forests to account
301 for the lowest bat activity of all habitats (~20 to 30 bat passes / h) whereas aquatic habitat
302 congregated the highest number of recordings (~ 300 bat passes /h).
303 Regarding bat species (h4), we found some interesting patterns. 6 species (*B. barbastellus*,
304 *Myotis* 50, PpygMin and all *Rhinolophus* spp.) were almost never found in mountain lakes, and
305 only made use of bottom aquatic habitats. From them, *Rhinolophus* spp. and *B. barbastellus*
306 have been pointed out not to go far away from forests, which could determine their complete
307 absence in top mountain ecosystems. Similarly, *Pippistrellus pygmaeus* Leach. has been found
308 to be tightly linked to riparian ecosystems, which could be the reason for its absence in
309 mountain lakes (Dietz and Kiefer 2016). Within these ‘bottom aquatic species’, PpygMin and
310 *Rhinolophus* spp. seemed to select rivers before reservoirs. This partially matches with the
311 findings of Russo and Jones (2003), who detected how *P. pygmaeus* and *M. schredibersii*
312 preferred rivers in their study. The reason why *Rhinolophus* spp. seemed to be partial to rivers
313 rather than lakes for hunting in our area, remains unclear. Contrary to this, *Plecotus* spp., *H.*

314 *savii* and *TadNyc*, were never found in rivers, and only selected both reservoirs and mountain
315 lakes to hunt (SD8), seeming to ‘lean towards’ going up 2000 m rather than foraging within the
316 nearby bottom rivers. This same community difference between rivers and lakes has been
317 supported by Ciechanowski (2002) in Polish Darzubska Forest. The probable preference of
318 both *T. teniotis* and *N. lasiopterus* for lakes and reservoirs rather than rivers could be due to
319 their big bodies and fast flying, which require a spaced habitat to manoeuvre (Dietz and Kiefer
320 2016). A similar matter could be occurring with *H. savii*, which has been found to select lakes
321 in Danube deltas rather than rivers (Pocora and Pocora 2011). Regarding *Plecotus* spp., those
322 feeding in mountain lakes probably account for *Plecotus macrobullaris* Kuz., which seem to
323 always spend the summer above the treeline in the Pyrenees (Alberdi et al. 2015). The reason
324 why *P. auritus* and *Plecotus austriacus* Fisch., which feed in lower altitudes, would select
325 reservoirs instead of rivers, remains unclear. All the above suggests that rivers and lakes, despite
326 all being aquatic habitats, account for relevant structural differences that make bat species select
327 them differently.

328 Finally, it is interesting to note that both *R. ferrumequinum* and *R. hipposideros*, which are said
329 to be rarely found above 1000 masl (Le Roux et al. 2016) were recorded in our study in
330 significantly higher altitudes. The point where we found the highest activity of *R. euryale* was
331 at ~ 2000 masl, and around 7 km away from bottom valleys (~850 masl). Knowing that *R.*
332 *euryale* roosts are usually below 800 masl makes us wonder what could be occurring. First,
333 detected bats could be segregated males that were avoiding competition from females, as has
334 been demonstrated with *R. hipposideros*. Second, these bats could just be adopting large
335 foraging areas from their roost sites (literature cites a medium foraging distance of ~4,3 to 10
336 km for the species). However, it remains astonishing that some individuals would climb up
337 1000 masl every night to feed, which returns us either for the sexual segregation explanation,
338 or the presence of particularly high roosting areas. Researchers also point out that *R. euryale*,

339 is the most thermophilic of all our *Rhinolophus* spp., which strictly avoids open areas and
340 coniferous forest but selects shrublands to hunt. This perfectly matches with our results, with
341 no evidence of any *Rinolophus* spp. within any forest or in open top mountain areas, but yes in
342 shrublands (Dietz and Kiefer 2016). Interestingly, *R. ferrumequinum*, which is cited to be less
343 thermophilic than *R. euryale* (Dietz and Kiefer 2016), was found in our study in lower sampling
344 points ~ 1300 m. *R. hipposideros* accounted for the higher locations ~2400 m, and was never
345 found hunting in forests, contradicting literature. In the case of *R. ferrumequinum*, higher
346 altitudes can be colonised (~1500 masl) but remains highly linked to open areas near the forest,
347 which again matches with its absence in mountain lakes (Dietz and Kiefer 2016).

348 Summarising, our study suggests that altitude, despite being a relevant predictor, remains
349 strongly subrogated to the habitat type, as their negative effects can be buffered within both
350 aquatic and forest habitats (h1). We also found how habitat richness peaked within the lowest
351 open habitats, probably due to their transition characteristics in between aquatic and forest
352 ecosystems (h2). Our results also support the idea of bats commuting from forests to aquatic
353 habitat for hunting (h3). Finally, we found species to generally fit within previous research
354 discoveries. However, we detected interesting patterns within aquatic habitat selection, and
355 unclear disparities of altitudinal feeding for *Rhinolophus* species.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Fig 1. Sampling points distribution along the Parc Natural de l'Alt Pirineu. Light yellow area shows the core protection zone of the PNAP.

Fig 2. Total activity of bats depending on habitat type. Red line and dots show the mean altitude for each habitat, also included within the y axis.

Fig 3. Richness of bats depending on habitat type. Red line and dots show the mean altitude for each habitat, also included within the y axis.

Fig 4. Relative position of habitat centroids respect each other. Centroids were obtained from the PCA sample points against bat species activity. Four groups are clearly differentiated within this graphic.

Fig 5. Disclosure of total bat activity (left) and richness (right), for all habitat types; forests (top), aquatic (middle), and open habitats (bottom).

Fig 6. Fixed effects graph-plotting of Altitude (left), Slope (middle), and Distance to water (right), in relation to Total Bat Activity (Top), and Bat Richness (Bottom).

TABLE LEGENDS

Table 1: Phonic group correspondence with most probable species in the area, as well as those bats that can be identified to the Species level. * Most probable species due to higher abundance in the PNAP. ** Most probable depending on the habitat type. *** Not found yet in the area.

Tables 2 and 3: summary tables for total activity model (left) and richness (right), for all sampling points.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL LEGENDS

SD1. Placing process of recording bats with Audiomoth records, which requires for an initial programming of devices, locating the recorder in the sampling point, and coming the next morning to collect it.

SD2. Some examples of the sampling habitats; montane hayfields, mountain lakes, and alpine grasslands.

SD3. *Barbastella barbastellus* ‘bat pass’, within a 5 s recorded audio file. The concept of ‘bat pass’ allows for a better standardization of data and comparing different nights.

SD4. Habitat bar-plots, filled with the relative proportions of each species calls.

SD5. PCA plotting of all sampling points, based on the relative activity of all bat species. Dots are filled with their corresponding habitat type.

SD6. Proportion of recorded species calls for all our samples.

SD7. Species bar-plotting, filled with the relative activity encountered within each habitat type.

SD8. Species bar-plotting, filled with the relative activity encountered within aquatic habitats.

SD9. Species bar-plotting, filled with the relative activity encountered within forests habitats.

SD10. Species bar-plotting, filled with the relative activity encountered within open habitats.

SD11. Best model predictor after performing model selection, for all models in all 6 situations.

SD12. Data table with all the information used for the present study analysis.

SD13. Developed R scripts used during this study.

SD14. Further research additional information. **SD15.** Limitations additional information.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Table 1

	Manual identification	Probable species	Other possible species.
Species	<i>Barbastella barbastellus</i>		
	<i>Hypsugo savii</i>		
	<i>Pipistrellus pipistrellus</i>		
	<i>Rhinolophus euryale</i>		
	<i>Rhinolophus ferrumequinum</i>		
	<i>Rhinolophus hipposideros</i>		
Phonic groups	EptNycVes	<i>Eptesicus serotinus</i> <i>Nyctalus leisleri</i>	<i>Nyctalus noctula</i> *** <i>Vespertilio murinus</i> ***
	<i>Plecotus</i> spp.	<i>Plecotus macrobularis</i> <i>Plecotus auritus</i> <i>Plecotus austriacus</i>	
	PippygMin	<i>Pippistrellus pygmaeus</i> <i>Miniopterus schreibersii</i>	
	Pipkuhnat	<i>Pipistrellus kuhlii</i>	<i>Pipistrellus nathusii</i> ***
	Myotis 50	<i>Myotis daubentonii</i> ** <i>Myotis mystacinus</i> ** <i>Myotis escaleraei</i>	<i>Myotis emarginatus</i> <i>Myotis capaccinii</i> <i>Myotis alcaethoe</i> *** <i>Myotis crypticus</i>
	Myotis 30	<i>Myotis myotis</i>	<i>Myotis blythii</i> ***
	TadNyc	<i>Tadarida teniotis</i>	<i>Nyctalus lasiopterus</i> ***

Tables 2 and 3

<i>Predictors</i>	Richness		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	7.21	6.59 – 7.82	<0.001
Altitude	-1.00	-1.79 – -0.21	0.014
Slope	-0.30	-0.95 – 0.34	0.350
Hillshade	-0.43	-1.05 – 0.19	0.169
Distance to water	-0.01	-0.71 – 0.69	0.977
Night temperature	0.15	-0.50 – 0.79	0.652
Random Effects			
σ^2	1.67		
τ_{00} Estació	3.08		
ICC	0.65		
$N_{\text{Estació}}$	49		
Observations	59		
Marginal R^2 / Conditional R^2	0.254 / 0.738		

<i>Predictors</i>	Total activity		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	147.40	88.32 – 206.47	<0.001
Altitude	-79.80	-151.28 – -8.33	0.029
Slope	-73.05	-134.43 – -11.67	0.021
Hillshade	2.18	-56.23 – 60.60	0.940
Distance to water	-40.42	-108.09 – 27.25	0.236
Night temperature	6.78	-39.13 – 52.70	0.768
Random Effects			
σ^2	5799.14		
τ_{00} Estació	37215.74		
ICC	0.87		
$N_{\text{Estació}}$	49		
Observations	59		
Marginal R^2 / Conditional R^2	0.319 / 0.908		